

NUTRI•KNOW

STRUVITE (IT)

GAS LOOP (IT)

RENURE (BE)

SOS_AQUAE
(IT)

POCKETBOER 2
(BE)

FERTICOOP-GO
(ES)

Grass2Algae
(BE)

Manure
Management
Tool (ES)

MOPS (IE)

Slurry
Concentrator
(ES)

Duncannon Blue
Flag Farming (IE)

Biorefinery
Glas (IE)

Exchanging easy-to-understand nutrient management knowledge with farmers

NUTRI-KNOW aims to improve nutrient management practices in agriculture by establishing an ongoing cycle of knowledge exchange for the benefit of both farmers and the environment.

Struvite

Livestock manure and digestate treatment to reduce emissions and produce struvite

STRUVITE operational group designed and implemented a prototype, a farm-scale system, capable of recovering struvite from agricultural digestate.

Challenge

Producing treated fractions which are less emissive in ammonia and greenhouse gas (methane and nitrous oxide) than the raw input digestate, particularly during the storage phase.

Activity

Monitoring the emissions reduction (ammonia, nitrous oxide, methane and odour) from the storage of the treated digestate fractions compared to the initial digestate.

Results

The reduced nitrogen content in the main treated fraction (supernatant clarified fraction) has allowed ammonia emissions to be reduced by 42% from storage, while the limited organic matter content resulted in a reduction of methane emissions from storage by 86%.

Pig digestate storage lagoon

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our journey!**

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